

NFDI4Earth

Deliverable D2.2.2

Concept for the NFDI4Earth User Support Network Ticketing System

Customization and implementation

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Executive summary

In this concept we will define the technical details (e.g.: name, response time, contact), rules and roles (e.g.: 1st-level- and 2nd-level-support), and certain answer types we expect for the basic internal support platform. The queue system will be based on the use of the support categories which have been defined together with M2.1 for the distribution of support requests to the support agents that have expertise in these categories. The documentation of the support standards and the internal communication between the agents is described. The annex contains templates for standard answers.

Abbreviations

GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation

LHB - Living Handbook

OTRS - Open Ticket Request System

TUDD - Technical University of Dresden

USN - User Support Network

ZIH - Center for information services and high performance computing

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1 Software

The User Support Network uses the OTRS ticket system hosted by TUDD-ZIH as software to manage user requests and respond to them. This was already committed within the application process of NFDI4Earth.

2 Naming

In order to ensure a clear differentiation of the area of operations and responsibility from the superordinate User Support Network (USN), the ticketing system itself is named: **Helpdesk**

3 Target group

The target groups of the Helpdesk are researchers (scientists), learners (students) and supporters (e.g. data stewards) of all earth system-related scientific disciplines.

4 Agents network

The group of Helpdesk agents consists of persons working at the partner institutions of the NFDI4Earth USN. The initial partners are described in the USN-Concept¹.

5 Team

5.1 Coordination Team

The coordination team consists of at least 2 people and their main task is to:

- represent a basic **internal contact** to the Helpdesk
- keep a general **overview of the processes** within the Helpdesk
- **ensure response** to all requests (tickets)
- **exchange information** between Helpdesk and User Support Network

¹ https://sharepoint.tu-dresden.de/projects/nfdi4earth/TA2/_2Facilitate/M2.2/_UserSupportNetwork/Concepts/N4-E-USN-Concept-20230128.docx?d=we06315f0a3b1459e8a7adc0d30cb54c8

5.2 1st-level-support

The 1st-level-support receives all incoming requests and is responsible for the initial reaction to these requests as well as potentially answering requests. We define 4 different categories of incoming requests (request categories) and describe the associated processing below (see 6.2.1).

The team of the 1st-level-support is rotating among the members of the Helpdesk. To prevent an inconsistent processing of requests, we aim to develop a guideline. (see 6.2.2)

5.2.1 Request categories

5.2.1.1 General request

These requests have a very general character and can be answered directly by the 1st-level-support (see template 11.5).

5.2.1.2 Content of the Living Handbook

The request is related to an article in the Living Handbook, and will be answered by referring to that article (see template 11.1).

5.2.1.3 Expert request

The request can only be answered by an expert and must therefore be forwarded to 2nd-level-support (see template 11.3).

5.2.1.4 Missing NFDI4Earth context

Requests that are not related to the NFDI4Earth topics will receive a response but will not be answered in terms of content (see template 11.4). The decision is made based on the following guideline.

5.2.2 Guideline

The 1st-level-support develops a guideline to document experiences on the one hand and ensure a uniform course of action, within the team of the 1st-level-support, on the other hand. That guideline aggregates information on how to:

- **respond directly**
- **find** the corresponding **request category**

- **find** the corresponding **queue** (resp. forward requests to 2nd-level-support)
- **document and find** requests and responses (*see chapter 8*)

5.3 2nd-level-support

The 2nd-level-support receives all subject specific requests, forwarded by the 1st-level-support. It consists of experts from the User Support Network, which are assigned to different queues. This assignment is based on the expertise of their institution. Further information on the related expertise can be found within the USN-Concept².

5.3.1 Queues

At the initial workshop of the USN we agreed on using a subset of the support categories. They are represented as queues within OTRS and are described in detail within the USN-Concept³. The first 3 categories ("Repositories", "Information and metadata", "Tools/Software") are matching best with the already existing support expertise of the participating institutions. For the categories "Services" and "Data and analysis" we expect less support possible from the current partners of the network but expect this to be covered in the near future. Therefore we will also have these ones in the first set of queues.

5.3.2 Outsourcing

Although we cover a wide range of expertise, we expect to face responses that cannot be answered by our experts. In this case, the 2nd-level-support can help to find external expertise and forwards the response outside of the Helpdesk, if necessary.

In relation to that, we define some guidelines:

1. an outsourced ticket is considered as completed and will be closed.
2. request unsolicited feedback in a final contact mail (*see template 11.6*)
3. the Helpdesk tries to get feedback if the response was well received after 2-3 weeks

We do not specify if such a feedback (see point 3) will be requested manually or automatically at this point.

² https://sharepoint.tu-dresden.de/projects/nfdi4earth/TA2/_2Facilitate/M2.2/_UserSupportNetwork/Concepts/N4E-USN-Concept-20230128.docx?d=we06315f0a3b1459e8a7adc0d30cb54c8

³ https://sharepoint.tu-dresden.de/projects/nfdi4earth/TA2/_2Facilitate/M2.2/_UserSupportNetwork/Concepts/N4E-USN-Concept-20230128.docx?d=we06315f0a3b1459e8a7adc0d30cb54c8

6 Contact

Contacting the OTRS ticketing system takes basically place via the central email address: helpdesk@nfdi4earth.de

There will be a central contact form in order to ensure a uniform and structured contact. This is the main point of contact to the Helpdesk and is located within the OneStop4All. The first publicly available version of this contact form contains the following (standard) fields:

- subject
- first and last name
- email address
- confirmation of the European GDPR
- the description of the specific concern.

The need for additional fields will be determined in regular evaluations within the Helpdesk (see chapter 9.2) and in cooperation with the other components of NFDI4Earth.

Although the central email address can of course be addressed from any form of mail client, the use of the contact form is the primary aim. Accordingly, this should also be part of the user interaction regulation of OneStop4All and Living Handbook.

The general procedure after the first contact triggers the following fundamental automatic steps:

- generation of a ticket within the OTRS ticketing system (incl. unique ID)
- message receipt confirmation (see template 11.2)

7 Response Time

The aim is to answer inquiries as soon as possible, within a maximum time of 3 days. However, thresholds need to be defined for reminder and evaluation processes:

1. An automated response will be triggered **immediately** after a ticket has been created, confirming the request and explaining the further procedure.
2. The 1st-level-support should respond within **3 working days**.
3. The 2nd-level-support should respond within the period of **10 working days**.

This does not necessarily mean that a request has to be answered or solved within this time, but to respond and get in contact.

8 Documentation and Evaluation

8.1 Documentation

All incoming requests and the corresponding responses are documented for the purpose of internal documentation, reviewing and reuse. This will be done chronological and topic related. The coordination team decides, which requests and responses will be documented and which have to be published internally or externally, depending on their relevance to the target group.

8.2 Evaluation

The Helpdesk needs regular evaluations to improve its quality and assess processes.

This can be done by automatically generated metrics like:

- response time
- length of communication process
- tickets per queue

Or by manual evaluations or discussions on topics like:

- guideline
- queues
- request categories
- collaboration with other NFDI4Earth components
- documentation
- response time thresholds
- templates

9 Internal Communication

9.1 Chat

There will be an **NFDI4Earth** Rocket.Chat Channel for the internal communication of the agents to allow instant contact between team members.

9.2 Virtual Jour fixe

All team members will take part in regular virtual meetings organized by the coordination team. The aim is to coordinate and evaluate the work of the Helpdesk based on questions like:

- Is there need for additional queues?
- Are all queues used?
- How long is the intermediate response time?
- What is the workload of the agents?
- Is the guideline helpful for the 1st-level-support?
- Do we need further metrics?

Exemplary evaluation criteria are described in chapter 9.

10 Appendix: Mail templates

The subject is build from:

- Ticketnumber
- Query

10.1 Link to Living Handbook

Dear Firstname/Lastname,

You can find a detailed answer to your inquiry in the following article:

Link to the article in the Living Handbook

With best regards, the **Helpdesk team**

Signature of the USN

10.2 Message inbox to 1st-level-support

Dear Firstname/Lastname,

We have received your ticket with the {number assigned automatically} The helpdesk colleagues will deal with your request and will get back to you as soon as possible!

With best regards, the **Helpdesk team**

Signature of the USN

10.3 Move from 1st-Level to 2nd-Level

Dear Firstname/Lastname,

Your ticket with the {number automatically assigned} was classified by us as follows:

-Ticket type: category chosen by 1st-level-support.

Since your request can only be handled by our experts, we will pass it on to our colleagues in the relevant department for further processing. An answer by this team will get back to you as soon as possible.

We ask you for a little patience, as the processing of your request may take some time.

With best regards **Name of the Staff of the s 1st-level-support team**

Signature of the USN

10.4 Request has no NFDI4Earth-context

Dear Firstname/Lastname,

In your request with the ticket {number automatically assigned}, no reference to the NFDI4Earth could be determined. Therefore we are not able to answer your request.

With best regards the team of the **Helpdesk**

Signature of the USN

10.5 Individual response by agent of 1st- or 2nd-level-support

Dear Firstname/Lastname

Individual answer

With best regards, the **Helpdesk team**

Signature of the USN

10.6 Outsourced request

Dear Firstname/Lastname

Unfortunately, we have to state that your request cannot be answered sufficiently.

However, we have tried to find a suitable external expert for you and offer you the following further contact options:

To improve the quality of our work, we would appreciate it if you could give us feedback irrespective of the outcome of your request.

With best regards, the **Helpdesk team**

Signature of the USN